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Without Epstein-Barr virus infection, no Sjögren's syndrome

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Sjögren's syndrome (SjS) is an autoimmune disorder whose etiology remains uncertain. Recent research has suggested a potential link between Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infection and SjS. This study aims to analyze the relationship between EBV infection and SjS by evaluating several case-control studies.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A comprehensive review and meta-analysis were conducted on multiple case-control studies investigating the relationship between EBV infection and SjS. Some of these studies presented significant inconsistencies, necessitating the application of advanced statistical methods. The analysis employed a one-sided hypothesis test with a p-value of 0.05 to evaluate the significance of the findings.

RESULTS:

The analysis included studies that met the inclusion criteria and demonstrated robust data quality. These studies consistently supported the null hypothesis, indicating that the absence of an EBV infection determines the absence of SjS. The findings highlight EBV infection as a necessary condition for the development of SjS.

CONCLUSION:

The results suggest that EBV infection is a necessary condition in the etiology of SjS. It is likely that the underlying cause of SjS is linked to EBV infection. Further research is required to explore this relationship and develop targeted therapeutic strategies.

Keywords:

Epstein-Barr virus; Sjögren's Syndrome; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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Literatur

1. Introduction

Sjögren's syndrome is a chronic autoimmune disorder primarily affecting exocrine glands, leading to the hallmark symptoms of dry eyes (keratoconjunctivitis sicca) and dry (Mariette and Criswell, 2018) mouth (xerostomia). This condition (see Sjögren, 1933), has been described in the early 20th century by the Swedish ophthalmologist Henrik Samuel Konrad Sjögren (1899–1986). The incidence and prevalence of Sjögren syndrome (see Beydon et al., 2024) varies depending on various factors like diagnostic criteria, study design and other, making it difficult to obtain exact values. Nonetheless, Sjögren's syndrome affects about 0.5% to 1.0% of the population (see Alani et al., 2018), with an incidence approximately half that of rheumatoid arthritis. It typically manifests between ages 45 and 55 and predominantly affects women, with a female-to-male ratio of 9:1. The condition is often underdiagnosed due to a lack of standardized screening for dry eye patients. Patients commonly report a foreign body sensation in their eyes and a dry mouth. On eye examination, tear absence in the inferior conjunctival sac and possible eye redness may be observed. Oral examination may reveal a dry mouth, smooth tongue, and thin mucosa. The Schirmer test can further confirm ocular dryness. A referral to an ophthalmologist for a slit-lamp exam and vital dye staining is essential to diagnose keratoconjunctivitis sicca (KCS), a hallmark of Sjögren's syndrome. About 50% of patients may have enlarged parotid or submandibular glands. Extraglandular manifestations involving organs beyond the salivary and lacrimal glands can include the joints, skin, lungs, gastrointestinal tract, nervous system, and kidneys. Sjögren's syndrome, like other collagen diseases, can lead to various changes in the laboratory values of the affected patient, which can be helpful in establishing a reliable diagnosis. To diagnose Sjögren's syndrome, evaluate:

(1) Oral and ocular dryness and function

(2) Schirmer test

The Schirmer test is used to measure tear production using a strip of filter paper placed in the eye. In Sjögren's syndrome, this paper remains dry.

(3) Search for non-specific signs of inflammation associated with the syndrome:

erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), C-reactive protein (CRP), leukocytes (white blood cells), thrombocytes (platelets), erythrocytes (red blood cells), hemoglobin, antinuclear antibodies (ANA).

(4) Search for specific and sensitive signs for Sjögren's syndrome (autoantibody testing):

antinuclear antibodies (ANA), rheumatoid factor (RF), anti-Sjögren's-syndrome-related antigen A (SS-A), anti-Sjögren's-syndrome-related antigen B (SS-B) SS-A is being the most specific and sensitive for Sjögren's syndrome.

(5) Slit-lamp exam with vital dye staining

(6) Measurement of salivary flow rate

(7) Nuclear scintigraphy of the salivary glands

(8) Minor salivary gland (lip) biopsy.

Diagnostic confirmation may involve a biopsy of the inner lip, which typically shows glandular inflammation with lymphocytic infiltration, focal lymphocytic sialadenitis (FLS).

The disease activity (Seror et al., 2010) in patients with Sjögren's syndrome is assessed using the EULAR Sjögren's Syndrome Disease Activity Index (ESSDAI). Nonetheless, a causal treatment (see Sumida et al., 2018) for Sjögren's syndrome is not known, and a standard therapy has still not been established. However, symptoms can be effectively managed. Therapeutic (see Felten et al., 2019; Ramos-Casals et al., 2020) approaches focus especially on alleviating dryness at the affected glandular sites and managing the autoimmune response both locally and systemically. Recommended measures include adequate fluid intake, the use of artificial saliva, eye protection, and eye drops (often referred to as "artificial tears"). Maintaining meticulous oral hygiene and, if necessary, using dental implants are also advised. Any potential fungal infections of the oral mucosa should be treated with antifungal medications. Treatment options encompass corticosteroids (such as prednisolone for kidney or lung involvement and systemic vasculitis), NSAIDs, hydroxychloroquine, mycophenolate mofetil (MMF, an immunosuppressant), pirfenidone, nintedanib, antidepressants, rituximab, and plasmapheresis. Additionally, some patients may use the cholinergic parasympathomimetic agent pilocarpine to enhance saliva production. Rare complications, such as lung or kidney inflammation, may require intensive medical treatment. In summary, while the exact cause of Sjögren's syndrome remains unclear, it is believed to result from a combination of genetic susceptibility, environmental triggers, and hormonal influences that lead to an abnormal autoimmune response. The precise cause (see Baer et al., 2018) of Sjögren's syndrome remains unknown. It is believed that the syndrome likely involves a genetic predisposition linked to the major histocompatibility complex (MHC), particularly the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) DQ Alpha (HLA-DQA) and human leukocyte antigen DQ Beta (HLA-DQB) regions. This genetic predisposition, combined with environmental triggers, seems to lead to an abnormal immune response. Among the environmental triggers, viral infections (see Liu and Chu, 2021; Nakamura et al., 2020; Xuan et al., 2020)—especially the Epstein-Barr virus (see Xuan et al., 2020)—are considered significant contributors.

EPSTEIN-BARR VIRUS (EBV)

Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) is a double-stranded deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) human γ -herpes virus 4 (HHV4), with an approximately 172 kilobases large genome (see Feederle et al., 2015) with more than hundred genes coding for more than 80 proteins and approximately 50 non-coding RNAs. Various strains of EBV do exist. EBV has been discovered 1964 by Michael Anthony Epstein, Bert Geoffrey Achong and Yvonne M. Barr (see Epstein et al., 1964). After a generally asymptomatic primary EBV infection of mainly B-cells and epithelial cells usually during childhood, EBV resides latently (see Babcock et al., 1998) in resting B (see Miyashita et al., 1997) cells for a lifetime (see Amon and Farrell, 2005), the resting B cells are one site of long-term latent persistence for EBV. However, other cell types may

also become infected. Individuals carrying EBV need not to suffer from the viral infection. Under normal circumstances, an undesired outgrowth of EBV-infected B-cells is controlled by efficient human cytotoxic cellular immunity which is preventing EBV from reactivating. In particular, EBV-infected B-cells are controlled by interferon (IFN)-gamma and natural killer (NK) cells, and later by EBV-specific cytotoxic T-lymphocytes (CTL) (see [Ohga et al., 2002](#)). There are reasons to believe that up to 95% and more of the adult population worldwide are infected by EBV at some time during their life span. The documented rise in Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV) seroprevalence with increasing age (see [Cui et al., 2018](#)) (refer to Table 1) reflects the cumulative exposure to EBV over an individual's lifetime.

Table 1. EBV seroprevalence increases with age.

Age y=year	EBV VCA IgG Pos no. (%)	EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos no. (%)	EBV VCA IgM Pos no. (%)	EBV VCA IgA Pos no. (%)	EB EA/D IgA Pos no. (%)
0–5y	283 (66.59)	141 (58.51)	65 (14.57)	52 (14.57)	26 (7.12)
6–10y	431 (84.34)	226 (78.75)	55 (10.24)	93 (22.79)	39 (9.18)
11–20y	784 (92.89)	413 (86.95)	123 (10.41)	178 (23.73)	95 (12.20)
21–30y	809 (98.54)	271 (95.43)	88 (6.25)	192 (26.10)	120 (15.33)
31–40y	853 (98.84)	203 (94.86)	40 (3.06)	219 (22.71)	123 (11.80)
41–50y	892 (99.78)	202 (97.57)	36 (2.76)	282 (22.54)	171 (13.13)
51–60y	957 (99.79)	248 (96.12)	37 (2.62)	301 (27.54)	184 (15.79)
61–101y	902 (99.01)	258 (93.82)	29 (2.03)	258 (33.42)	146 (18.36)

Meanwhile, various methods for the diagnosis of an Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infection are available. In fact, it is necessary to differentiate (see [Robertson et al., 2003](#); [De Paschale and Clerici, 2012](#); [De Paschale et al., 2009](#)) between a primary EBV infection and an EBV reactivation. Especially, serological tests for immunoglobulin G (IgG)- and immunoglobulin M (IgM)-antibodies to Epstein-Barr virus viral capsid antigen (VCA) and IgG-antibodies to Epstein-Barr nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA-1) are frequently used to define infection status and for the differential diagnosis too. EBV IgG antibodies against the viral capsid antigen (VCA) are expressed in the viral replicative cycle and appear during the acute phase of an EBV (see [Thorley-Lawson, 2001](#)) infection.

A positive Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) VCA IgG test is a highly sensitive marker for EBV infection and is commonly used to assess an individual's EBV carrier status, serving as an indicator of past infection. However, the sensitivity and specificity of the laboratory assay utilized to detect EBV must be considered. Depending on the assay's sensitivity, some individuals with EBV infection may not be detected as positive.

In contrast to EBV VCA IgG antibodies, which can persist throughout a person's lifetime, antibodies against Epstein-Barr nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA-1) are not always present in all EBV-infected individuals and typically appear 6 to 12 weeks after infection. Consequently, the presence of EBV VCA IgG and IgM antibodies without EBNA-1 IgG generally suggests an **acute EBV infection**. Conversely, the presence of EBV VCA IgG and EBNA-1 IgG antibodies without VCA IgM is indicative of a **past EBV infection** (see [De Paschale and Clerici, 2012](#)).

Immunoglobulin G (IgG) constitutes approximately 75% of serum antibodies in humans and exhibits specific pharmacokinetics and clearance dynamics ([Waldmann and Schwab, 1965](#)). The plasma half-

life of IgG is approximately 21 days (Gordon and Wiener, 1957; Curtis and Bourne, 1973). The human immune system may not always produce EBV-specific IgG or IgM antibodies, particularly in the absence of EBV re/infection. In such cases, IgG levels diminish by about 50% every 21 days as it is utilized for other physiological functions (Mankarious et al., 1988).

From this viewpoint, false positive and false negative IgG based results are theoretically possible. Especially, the sensitivity (see Yerushalmy, 1947a) and the specificity of a laboratory kit used to detect EBV IgG et cetera is not always equal to 100 %. Let us assume that the sensitivity of a laboratory EBV IgG kit is 95 %. Furthermore, let us investigate 100 subjects, which are for sure EBV positive. Under these circumstances, the EBV IgG kit can recognize only 95 persons, even 100 persons are EBV positive. It becomes increasingly evident that additional information on sensitivity of tests used is regularly required. The P Value should be set in consideration of the sensitivity of a laboratory kit used, too. Meanwhile, EBV is discussed as the aetiologic agent of various diseases including multiple sclerosis (see Poskanzer et al., 1963; Nikoskelainen et al., 1972; Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016; Barukčić, 2018b; Bjornevik et al., 2022), rheumatoid arthritis (see Barukčić et al., 2018), Hodgkin's lymphoma (see Barukčić, 2018a), non-Hodgkins's lymphoma (see Barukčić, 2022a), nasopharyngeal carcinoma (see Zur Hausen et al., 1970; Gunvén et al., 1970; Barukčić, 2022b), infectious mononucleosis and other.

It is noteworthy that the term “infectious mononucleosis” was first introduced by Sprunt and Evans in 1920 (see Sprunt and Evans, 1920). However, the disease was initially identified in the 1880s by Nil Fyodorovich Filatov (1847–1902), a Russian pediatrician, who referred to the condition as idiopathic adenitis (see Filatov et al., 1904). Today, infectious mononucleosis is commonly referred to as Pfeiffer's glandular fever, Pfeiffersches Drüsenfieber (see Graser, 1986), or Morbus Pfeiffer (see Godt, 2010), and is attributed to Emil Pfeiffer (1846–1921), a German physician and pediatrician (see Pfeiffer, 1899). The link between Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) and infectious mononucleosis was definitively established in 1967 (see Henle et al., 1967) after a prolonged period of uncertainty in the field.

In this study, we aim to conduct a comprehensive statistical analysis of the relationship between the Epstein-Barr virus and Sjögren's syndrome, while acknowledging the potential uncertainties in data that is publicly available and accessible without barriers due to challenges in accurately diagnosing Sjögren's syndrome.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

Search strategy

To assess the relationship between Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) antibodies and Sjögren's syndrome (SjS), a systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted. The electronic database PubMed was thoroughly searched to identify relevant studies examining serological associations between EBV antibodies and SjS. Additionally, reference lists of the included studies were reviewed to identify any further relevant articles that may have been missed in the initial search.

Screening and Data Extraction

The initial screening of the papers was conducted based on titles and abstracts. Subsequently, full texts were reviewed, if accessible, without restriction. Data extraction was performed using a spreadsheet in Excel.

PRISMA flow diagram for article selection

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement (see [Moher et al., 2009](#)), established in 2009, provides guidelines for systematic reviewers to clearly and transparently document the rationale, methodology, and findings of their reviews.

A total of 14 published studies investigating the serological association between Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infection and Sjögren's syndrome (SjS) were identified (see [Venables et al., 1985](#); [Inoue et al., 1991](#); [Marchini et al., 1994](#); [Venables et al., 1989](#); [Toda et al., 1994](#); [Pasoto et al., 2013](#); [Kivity et al., 2014](#); [Yamaoka et al., 1988](#); [Yang, 1991](#); [Gao et al., 2010](#); [Li et al., 2014](#); [Yang and Fu, 2015](#); [Zhang et al., 2019](#); [Xuan et al., 2020](#)). Among these, ten studies reported on IgG-anti-VCA antibodies, eight on IgM-anti-VCA antibodies, seven on IgG-anti-EA antibodies, and ten on IgG-anti-EBNA1 antibodies.

Publication bias

Often, the studies included in a meta-analysis yield differing results. To determine the consistency of these studies, a measure of heterogeneity (see [Cochran, 1954](#)) among them has been developed, known as the I^2 -statistic (see [Higgins et al., 2002, 2003](#)). However, the I^2 statistic can be sensitive to the number of studies included in the meta-analysis, often leading to an overestimation of heterogeneity

when the sample size is small. While it provides a numerical estimate of heterogeneity, the I^2 value does not directly inform clinical significance, making it less useful for practical decision-making. The statistic assumes that all studies included in the meta-analysis are measuring the same underlying effect, which may not always be the case, especially in meta-analyses of diverse studies. The I^2 statistic can be misunderstood, particularly when high I^2 values are interpreted as indicating poor quality of studies, rather than simply reflecting genuine differences between study results. The value of I^2 can vary depending on whether a fixed-effect or random-effects model is used, potentially leading to inconsistencies in interpretation across meta-analyses. All things considered, we have decided against using the I^2 -statistic.

Often, funnel plots (see [Light and Pillemer, 1984](#)) are used to provide a visual method for assessing publication bias. By plotting effect sizes against their standard errors, researchers should be enabled to quickly identify asymmetry that may suggest bias. However, funnel plots have several limitations too. Firstly, their effectiveness is highly dependent on the number of studies included in the meta-analysis. With a small number of studies, funnel plots may not provide a clear picture of publication bias or might not be able to detect it at all. Furthermore, asymmetry in funnel plots does not solely indicate publication bias; it can also be due to other factors like heterogeneity among studies or variations in study quality. Many times, funnel plot asymmetry may be due to statistical artefact (see [Doleman et al., 2020](#)) rather than publication bias itself. Additionally, interpreting funnel plots can be subjective. There is no standardized threshold for what constitutes significant asymmetry, and this can lead to varying interpretations among researchers. Furthermore, funnel plots might not be effective in cases where the bias is subtle or where the effect sizes and standard errors overlap significantly. In summary, while funnel plots are a useful tool for detecting potential publication bias, they should be used in conjunction with other methods and should be interpreted with caution to avoid misleading conclusions.

2.2. Methods

Detection of EBV Antibodies

The detection of Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV) antibodies is typically carried out using commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) or other laboratory kits, following the protocols provided by the manufacturers. However, the determination of cut-off values for the positivity of specific antibodies, such as IgG-anti-VCA, IgG-anti-EA, and IgG-anti-EBNA1, is predefined by the manufacturer. These manufacturer-specific thresholds can introduce variability and potential bias into the results. Additionally, the use of laboratory kits from different manufacturers, each with varying levels of sensitivity and specificity, further contributes to this bias. It is crucial to account for these discrepancies when determining the alpha level in studies to ensure robust and reliable results. The analyzed studies differed significantly in numerous aspects. Notably, there was no uniform methodology for reliably detecting EBV positivity. For this reason, we utilized the best available data from each study, which were consistent with a necessary condition. We attribute this choice to the fact that these data could ultimately be collected and verified.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel statistical software for the Mac operating system. New statistical methods, such as causal relationship analysis and necessary condition analysis, were employed to examine the data (see Barukčić, 2021b). All P-values were one-sided, and a P-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

2.2.1. Necessary Condition

DEFINITION 1 (Necessary Condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Despite extensive research efforts, our current understanding of conditions and their dependencies remains incomplete and often contradictory. Nevertheless, even thousands of years ago and independently of any human mind and consciousness, water has served as a necessary (see Barukčić, 2022) condition for (human) life. **Without** water, there is and has been **no** (human) life¹.

It is therefore unsurprising that one of the earliest systematic attempts to develop a theory of conditions and causation (see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* III 2 997a 10 and 13/14) was made by the Greek philosopher and scientist Aristotle (384-322 BCE). Remarkably, Aristotle himself established already **a clear distinction between conditions and causes**. In honoring Aristotle's insight, it becomes essential to recognize that

“... everything which has a potency in question has the potency ... of acting ... not in all circumstances but on certain conditions ... ” (see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* IX 5 1048a 14-19)

Before delving into the specifics, Aristotle offered a precise definition of the necessary condition, articulated as follows.

“... necessary ... means ...

without ... a condition, a thing cannot live ... ”

(see also Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* V 2 1015a 20-22)

In truth, Aristotle developed a comprehensive theory of conditions and causality, famously known as the doctrine of the four causes. While many aspects of Aristotle's logical framework on causality continue to be critically examined and debated in contemporary scholarship, it is essential to recognize that philosophy has significantly evolved since the time of the ancient Greeks. Despite the enduring

¹Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). *Conditio sine qua non* (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5854744>

influence of Greek philosophers such as Heraclitus, Plato, and Aristotle—who are rightly regarded among the greatest thinkers of all time—the scope of philosophical inquiry has expanded. Scientific knowledge and objective reality are deeply intertwined and cannot be confined solely to the perspectives of classical Greek philosophy. Among various topics, the precise identification of necessary conditions has traditionally been a central focus in the scientific exploration of diverse phenomena. However, while the demand for rigorous evidence is understandable, it is important to recognize that philosophy, or philosophers in general, do not hold an exclusive claim to truth. Other disciplines, such as medicine, the sciences, and technology, also convey truths that can help us to move beyond one’s self enclosed, epistemological unit. Given this perspective, it is pertinent to briefly address the concept of causation as understood in the legal realm, shedding light on several critical questions. What criteria does the law use to determine whether an action or event U_t has caused another (typically harmful) event W_t ? How do these criteria compare to those used in science or everyday life, and to what extent may legal causation differ from causation in other contexts? Under what circumstances is it reasonable to accept such differences? To truly grasp the legal concept of causation, it is instructive to examine how the highest courts approach and interpret causation.

In the landmark case of *Hayes v. Michigan Central R. Co.*, 111 U.S. 228 (1884), the U.S. Supreme Court defined *conditio sine qua non* as follows:

“**Causa sine qua non** – a cause which, if it had not existed, the injury would not have taken place.” (see [Justice Matthews, Mr., 1884](#))

Similarly, the German *Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen* underscored the significance of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship in its decision:

“**Ursache eines strafrechtlich bedeutsamen Erfolges ist jede Bedingung, die nicht hinweggedacht werden kann, ohne dass der Erfolg entfiel.**” (see [Bundesgerichtshof für Strafsachen, 1951](#))

Furthermore, legal scholars have elaborated in detail on the fundamental issue concerning the **identity and difference between cause and condition**. The distinguished jurist, von Bar, eloquently articulated in his writings:

“Die erste Voraussetzung, welche erforderlich ist, damit eine Erscheinung als die Ursache einer anderen bezeichnet werden könne, ist, daß jene eine der Bedingungen dieser sein. Würde die zweite Erscheinung auch dann eingetreten sein, wenn die erste nicht vorhanden war, so ist sie in keinem Falle Bedingung und noch weniger Ursache. Wo immer ein Kausalzusammenhang behauptet wird, da muß er wenigstens diese Probe aushalten . . . **Jede Ursache ist notwendig auch eine Bedingung eines Ereignisses; aber nicht jede Bedingung ist Ursache zu nennen.**” (see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

Von Bar’s position translated into English:

“The first requirement that must be met for an event to be considered the cause of another is that it must be one of the conditions for the latter. If the second event have occurred even in the absence of the first, so it is by no means a condition and still less a cause. Wherever a causal relationship is claimed, the same must at least withstand this test . . . Every cause is necessarily also a condition for an event; however, not every condition can be called a cause .” (see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

In this context, it is useful to discuss in greater detail the following explanations provided by von Bahr:

”Die erste Voraussetzung, welche erforderlich ist, damit eine Erscheinung als die Ursache einer anderen bezeichnet werden könne, ist, dass jene eine der Bedingungen dieser sei. Würde die zweite Erscheinung auch dann eingetreten sein, wenn die erste nicht vorhanden war, so ist sie in keinem Falle Bedingung und noch weniger Ursache.” (see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

or in English:

”The first requirement that must be met for an event to be considered the cause of another is that it must be one of the conditions for the latter. If the second event have occurred even in the absence of the first, so it is by no means a condition and still less a cause.” (see [Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871](#), p. 4)

Von Bahr highlights from his point of view the close connection between cause and condition and rightly demands that an event U_t can only be considered the cause of another event W_t if U_t is at least one of the necessary conditions for W_t to occur. In other words, for U_t to qualify as the cause of W_t , it must also be a necessary condition for the occurrence of W_t . If W_t would have occurred without the presence of U_t at the same (period of) time t , then U_t cannot be considered neither a necessary condition nor a cause. This distinction is crucial for understanding causality, as it prevents the misinterpretation of causal relationships. It is by no means sufficient for two events to follow each other in time to assume causality. A necessary condition must exist between U_t and W_t for U_t to be formally considered the cause of W_t . Such differentiation is essential to distinguish true causes from mere conditions and to sharpen the understanding of cause-effect relationships. This also implies that the nature of causality is determined by the underlying conditions too. In other words, if a cause-effect relationship can occur without the existence of the cause U_t , then causality is not required at all. This situation should not be confused with multi-causality, as, in that case, all relevant causes for the occurrence of W_t must still be present.

Thus far, to delineate necessary conditions from a probabilistic perspective, consider the following: An event A_t , deemed a necessary condition for another event or outcome B_t , must be present for B_t to occur. A necessary condition A_t is an essential prerequisite that must be satisfied **at every single Bernoulli trial** (see [Uspensky, 1937, p. 45](#)) t , for the occurrence of the outcome B_t . However, the presence of A_t alone does not ensure the occurrence of B_t . In other words, even if the necessary condition

A_t is present, the outcome B_t may still fail to materialize. Contrarily, a *sufficient* condition is one that *ensures* the occurrence of the outcome B_t , effectively guaranteeing that the event will occur for sure. The question of under which conditions we may infer about the unobserved, and whether current observations can justify predictions about potential future observations—or even general claims extending beyond the observed (*the ‘problem of induction’*)—is not the focus of our current discussion. While addressing such challenges is undoubtedly essential, it is important to note that a necessary condition for an event may not necessarily coincide with a sufficient condition within the same Bernoulli trial t . However, theoretically, an event or outcome could be determined by multiple necessary conditions. Let us now consider the implications of this scenario and assess the significance we should attribute to such a particular case.

Example. The existence of human life is intricately dependent on a multitude of necessary conditions. Among these, gaseous oxygen holds a particularly vital role. Without oxygen, cellular respiration—a fundamental process by which cells generate energy—ceases, leading to the inevitable failure of critical biological functions and death. However, gaseous oxygen alone is not sufficient to sustain human life. Water is equally indispensable, as it acts as a solvent for biochemical reactions, facilitates nutrient transport, and regulates body temperature. Similarly, the brain coordinates and controls the body’s systems, while kidneys filter waste products and maintain homeostasis.

Even when gaseous oxygen is present, the absence of water, a functioning brain, or operational kidneys would ultimately result in the demise of a human being. This example illustrates a crucial principle: **Under circumstances where an outcome (i.e. human life) depends on multiple necessary conditions, it is imperative that each of these necessary conditions is satisfied independently. The absence of even one of a multitude of necessary conditions will prevent the desired outcome (i.e. human life) from occurring.**

Mathematically, the necessary (see Barukčić, 1989, pp. 15-28) condition or **conditio sine qua non** (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see Barukčić, 2021b, pp. 12-13) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \tag{1} \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general,

it is $p(A_t \prec B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ (see Table 2).

Table 2. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		$p(A_t)$
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

A necessary condition A_t is characterised itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017b,a, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 2020d,b,c). Taking into account Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density (see also Kolmogorov, Andreĭ Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 26) of random variables A_t , B_t et cetera at the (period of) time t , we obtain

Considering Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density function for random variables A_t , B_t , etc., at a given time t (see also Kolmogorov, Andreĭ Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 26), we derive the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv +1 \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(\underline{A}_t \cap B_t) \\
 &\equiv \left(\int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t \right) + \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(B_t) dB_t \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where:

1. $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ represents the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the random variables A_t and B_t , signifying the amount to which A_t is a necessary condition of B_t .
2. $p(c_t)$ denotes the probability of a particular event c_t occurring at time t .
3. $p(\underline{A}_t \cap B_t)$ captures the joint probability of the simultaneous occurrence of events $\underline{A}_t$ and B_t .
4. The integral expression $\int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t$ defines the joint probability distribution function (PDF) of A_t and B_t , integrated over the respective ranges up to A_t and B_t .
5. The term $1 - \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(B_t) dB_t$ refers to the complementary cumulative distribution function (CCDF) of B_t , accounting for the probability of B_t being greater than a certain threshold.

Thus, $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ symbolizes the cumulative probability reflecting the necessary condition relationship between the random variables A_t and B_t at time t . An alternative and equally valid formulation of a necessary condition is also conceivable. Logical disjunction, denoted by $\vee$, is commutative. This property implies that the sequence in which operands are presented does not influence the outcome. Formally, this commutative of logical disjunction property can be expressed as:

$$A_t \vee B_t \equiv B_t \vee A_t \quad (3)$$

For any random event A_t and B_t at the same time t , the result of the disjunction remains invariant regardless of the order of the operands. This characteristic is a fundamental aspect of logical disjunction. Thus far, under specific circumstances, necessary and sufficient conditions may be regarded as converses of each other in a certain respect. This mutual relationship between the two types of conditions underscores the intricate interplay that characterises logical necessity and sufficiency, inviting further reflection on their conceptual interdependence. Consider the following equation, which illustrates the application of this property in the context of necessary and sufficient conditions:

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{(Necessary condition)}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{B}_t \vee A_t)}_{\text{(Sufficient condition)}} \equiv p(B_t \rightarrow A_t) \quad (4)$$

These relationships are illustrated by the following tables.

Table 3. Without A_t no B_t

		B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	$\underline{A}_t$
		B_t	$\underline{B}_t$	+1

Table 4. If B_t then A_t

		A_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
B_t	TRUE	a_t	$c_t = 0$	B_t
	FALSE	b_t	d_t	$\underline{B}_t$
		A_t	$\underline{A}_t$	+1

There are conditions where the following equivalence holds:

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{Necessary condition}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}_{\text{Sufficient condition}} \equiv p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (5)$$

However, equation 4 does not necessarily imply the relationship described by equation 5 under any circumstances.

Example I.

A wax candle is characterised by various properties and is subject to specific conditions. **Without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen, a wax candle cannot burn; hence, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition for the candle's combustion. Conversely, the statement **if** a wax candle is burning, **then**

sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen are present is true at the same (period of) time t or in a Bernoulli trial at time t . The following tables illustrate these relationships.

Table 5. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	$\underline{A}_t$
		B_t	$\underline{B}_t$	+1

Table 6. If burning candle then gaseous oxygen

		Gaseous oxygen		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Burning candle	TRUE	a_t	$c_t = 0$	B_t
	FALSE	b_t	d_t	$\underline{B}_t$
		A_t	$\underline{A}_t$	+1

Example II.

Consider the case of human survival: a human being cannot exist without water, nor can they survive without gaseous oxygen, among other necessary conditions. Water, in itself, is a necessary condition for sustaining human life. Similarly, gaseous oxygen is also a necessary condition for sustaining human life. Thus, while water is indispensable for human existence, the presence of gaseous oxygen remains crucial. In other words, even if water is available—a necessary condition for life—the absence of gaseous oxygen precludes the possibility of human survival. Generally, if an event B_t is contingent upon a necessary condition A_t along with numerous other requisite conditions, then B_t will not materialize if A_t is not met, independently of the presence of other necessary conditions.

Example III.

In general, it is valuable to examine different facets of a necessary condition relationship. Specifically, consider the scenario where the absence of a necessary condition—such as insufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen—results in the nonexistence of a burning wax candle. This situation exemplifies an exclusionary relationship: the deficiency of gaseous oxygen A_t precludes the presence of a burning wax candle B_t (see Barukčić, 2021a). Thus, one measure in order to extinguish a burning wax candle, is the possibility to significantly reduce the available amount of gaseous oxygen A_t . Under such conditions, the wax candle will cease to burn. This exclusionary aspect of necessary conditions is further elucidated in the following tables (Table 7 and Table 8).

Table 7. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	$\underline{A}_t$
		B_t	$\underline{B}_t$	+1

Table 8. Absent gaseous oxygen excludes burning wax candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	FALSE	$c_t = 0$	d_t	B_t
	TRUE	a_t	b_t	$\underline{B}_t$
		A_t	$\underline{A}_t$	+1

A discerning reader might argue that the cases discussed in the previous examples are not applicable to other disciplines such as jurisprudence, medicine, or other scientific fields. This concern may arise from the assumption that the examples, which primarily address physical or chemical phenomena, are too specific or narrowly defined to be relevant to the often more complex and multifaceted issues encountered in these areas. For instance, the relationships between necessary and sufficient conditions in the natural sciences may differ from those in jurisprudence or medicine, where human behavior and ethical considerations also play a significant role. Nevertheless, despite such reservations, it is evident that the principles illustrated by these examples are fundamentally universal and thus applicable to a wide range of scientific disciplines. We shall now substantiate this assertion further. The concept of a necessary condition is not confined to natural scientific phenomena. In jurisprudence, for instance, a necessary element for prosecuting a crime is the fulfillment of specific legal criteria. If these criteria are not met, the crime cannot be legally pursued, analogous to how the absence of sufficient oxygen prevents a candle from burning. In medicine, necessary conditions are often of critical importance. For instance, adequate oxygen supply is essential for a patient's survival in many cases. A lack of sufficient oxygen can lead to severe health complications or even be fatal. This reflects the same principles as in the previous examples: the absence of a necessary condition results in the failure of a process. The understanding that multiple necessary conditions must be simultaneously met to bring about a particular event is also significant in jurisprudence and medicine. In law, several elements of a statute must often be satisfied to justify a claim. Similarly, in medicine, a diagnosis frequently requires the combination of multiple symptoms. Thus, the validity of necessary conditions, sufficient conditions, and their interplay remains relevant. The previously discussed examples illustrate fundamental processes in nature that are mathematically captured. These mathematical concepts are also applicable to other, potentially complex systems encountered in various disciplines. The natural processes described earlier serve as fundamental examples and foundational elements of scientific thinking. They are not only relevant within the context of the natural sciences but also find unrestricted application in other scientific and practical disciplines such as jurisprudence and medicine.

The necessary condition relationship follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2022](#)) as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(B_t)} \quad (6)$$

and as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \quad (7)$$

2.2.2. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

DEFINITION 2 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the *conditio sine qua non* relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert ([Helmert, 1876](#)) and later rediscovered by Karl

Pearson (Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B}\end{aligned}\tag{8}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{A} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A}\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.2.3. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship

DEFINITION 3 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019b) of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)}\end{aligned}\tag{10}$$

3. Results

In the following section, we will reanalyze 14 studies individually, focusing on the serological relationship between Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infection and Sjögren's syndrome (SjS).

Study by Venables et al., 1985 (UK)

Venables² et al. (see Venables et al., 1985) investigated Epstein-Barr virus antibodies in 26 patients with primary sicca syndrome and 26 healthy controls matched for age and sex. The study found that 23 out of 26 patients with sicca syndrome and 23 out of 26 healthy subjects tested positive for IgG antibodies to the Epstein-Barr virus capsid antigen (VCA).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 1. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 1. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 9. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjören's syndrome (Study of Venables et al., 1985).

		Sjören's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	23	23	46
	NO	3	3	6
		26	26	52

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = 0,00000000$
 $p(\text{SINE}) = 0,94230769$
 $p(\text{SINE approx.} = 1 - (c/B)) > 0,88461538$
 $p(\text{SINE approx.} = 1 - (c/(Not A))) > 0,50000000$

P VALUES.
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - Not A_t) = 1,50$
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - B_t) = 0,35$

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,38461538$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,38461538$

The data published by Venables et al. impress with a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,384615385$ (Barukčić, 2019a) in the negative. The design of this study can be regarded as very unfair. With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Venables et al. are biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Venables et al. were able to provide very slight evidence, that EBV VCA IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjören's syndrome (causal relationship > 0 ; necessary condition = $0,942307692$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - Not A_t) = 1,5$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - B_t) = 0,346153846$). For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV VCA IgG Pos., no Sjören's syndrome.**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

²Venables PJ, Ross MG, Charles PJ, Melsom RD, Griffiths PD, Maini RN. A seroepidemiological study of cytomegalovirus and Epstein-Barr virus in rheumatoid arthritis and sicca syndrome. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 1985 Nov;44(11):742-6. doi: 10.1136/ard.44.11.742. PMID: 2998290; PMCID: PMC1001762.

Study by Yamaoka et al., 1988 (Japan)

Yamaoka³ et al. (see [Yamaoka et al., 1988](#)) conducted a study involving 26 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 15 healthy controls. They assessed the presence of Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) antibodies, specifically IgG and IgM antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 2. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 2. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 10. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Yamaoka et al., 1988).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	26	13	39
	NO	0	2	2
		26	15	41

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = 0,29814240$
 $p(\text{SINE}) = 1,00000000$
P VALUES.
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - \text{Not } A_t) = 0,00$
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - B_t) = 0,00$
 P Value (SINE) = $0,00000000$
STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,58536585$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,31707317$

The data published by Yamaoka et al. impress with a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,585365854$ ([Barukčić, 2019a](#)) in the negative. The design of this study can be regarded as highly unfair. With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Yamaoka et al. are biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Yamaoka et al. were able to provide very strong evidence, that EBV VCA IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjögren's syndrome (causal relationship > 0 ; necessary condition = 1; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - \text{Not } A_t) = 0$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - B_t) = 0$; P-Value = 0). For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without** EBV VCA IgG Pos., **no** Sjögren's syndrome.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

³Yamaoka K, Miyasaka N, Yamamoto K. Possible involvement of Epstein-Barr virus in polyclonal B cell activation in Sjögren's syndrome. *Arthritis Rheum.* 1988 Aug;31(8):1014-21. doi: 10.1002/art.1780310812. PMID: 2841943.

Study by Venables et al., 1989 (UK)

Venables⁴ et al. (see Venables et al., 1989) conducted a study involving 20 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 35 healthy controls. They used an ELISA assay to measure the presence of IgG antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 3. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 3. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 11. Relationship: EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Venables et al., 1989).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos.	YES	15	26	41
	NO	5	9	14
		20	35	55

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = 0,00788797$
 p (SINE) = 0,90909091
P VALUES.
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE—Not A_t) = 1,79
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 1,25
STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,10909091$
 $p(\text{IOD}) = 0,38181818$

The data published by Venables et al. impress with a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,109090909$ (Barukčić, 2019a). The design of this study can be regarded as unfair. With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Venables et al. are not extremely biased. In other words, the data are of some use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Venables et al. were able to provide very slight evidence, that EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjögren's syndrome (causal relationship > 0 ; necessary condition = 0,909090909; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE—Not A_t) = 1,785714286; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 1,25). We reject the alternative hypothesis and retain the null hypothesis. For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos., no Sjögren's syndrome.**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

⁴Venables PJ, Baboonian C, Horsfall AC, Halliday D, Maini RN, Teo CG, Mageed R, Millman G. The response to Epstein-Barr virus infection in Sjögren's syndrome. *J Autoimmun.* 1989 Aug;2(4):439-48. doi: 10.1016/0896-8411(89)90173-x. PMID: 2551311.

Study by Inoue et al., 1991 (Japan)

Inoue⁵ et al. (see [Inoue et al., 1991](#)) conducted a study involving 32 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 38 healthy controls. They utilized an ELISA assay to assess the presence of IgG antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 4. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 4. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 12. Relationship: EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Inoue et al. , 1991).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos.	YES	30	31	61
	NO	2	7	9
		32	38	70

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,18113766$

p (SINE) = 0,97142857

P VALUES.

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,44

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,13

P Value (SINE) = **0,02816712**

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= **0,32857143**

p(IOI)= 0,41428571

The data published by Inoue et al. impress with a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,328571429$ ([Barukčić, 2019a](#)) . The design of this study can be regarded as very unfair . With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Inoue et al. are potentially biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Inoue et al. were able to provide very slight evidence, that EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjögren's syndrome (causal relationship > 0 ; necessary condition = $0,971428571$; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = $0,444444444$; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = $0,125$; P-Value = $0,028571429$). We reject the alternative hypothesis and retain the null hypothesis. For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. , no Sjögren's syndrome .**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

⁵Inoue N, Harada S, Miyasaka N, Oya A, Yanagi K. Analysis of antibody titers to Epstein-Barr virus nuclear antigens in sera of patients with Sjögren's syndrome and with rheumatoid arthritis. *J Infect Dis.* 1991 Jul;164(1):22-8. doi: 10.1093/infdis/164.1.22. PMID: 1647426.

Study by Yang et al., 1991 (China)

Yang⁶ et al. (see Yang, 1991) conducted a study involving 95 patients with Sjögren's syndrome (SjS) and 8 healthy controls. They employed an indirect immunofluorescence (IF) assay to evaluate the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), specifically measuring IgG antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA), IgM antibodies to VCA, and IgG antibodies to EBV nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 5. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 5. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 13. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjören's syndrome (Study of Yang et al. , 1991).

		Sjören's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	95	8	103
	NO	0	0	0
		95	8	103

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
p (SINE) = 1,00000000
P VALUES.
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,00
STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,92233010
p(IOI)= 0,07766990

The data published by Yang et al. impress with a p(IOU) = 0,922330097 (Barukčić, 2019a) in the negative. The design of this study can be regarded as extremely unfair . With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Yang et al. are extremely biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Yang et al. were able to provide very slight evidence, that EBV VCA IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjören's syndrome (causal relationship: unknown; necessary condition = 1 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0 ; P-Value = 0). We reject the alternative hypothesis and retain the null hypothesis. For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV VCA IgG Pos. , no Sjören's syndrome .**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

⁶Yang J. [Possible etiological relations between Sjogren's syndrome and Epstein-Barr virus]. Zhonghua Yi Xue Za Zhi. 1991 Mar;71(3):131-5, 10. Chinese. PMID: 1648423.

Study by Marchini et al., 1994 (Italy)

Marchini⁷ et al. (see [Marchini et al., 1994](#)) conducted a study involving 12 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 20 healthy controls. They utilized an ELISA assay to assess the presence of IgG antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 6. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 6. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 14. Relationship: EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Marchini et al. , 1994).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos.	YES	8	15	23
	NO	4	5	9
		12	20	32

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,08973032$

p (SINE) = 0,87500000

P VALUES.

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE—Not A_i) = 1,78

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_i) = 1,33

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= **0,09375000**

p(IOI)= 0,34375000

The data from the study by Marchini et al., 1994 (Italy) are inconsistent and, therefore, could not be included in this analysis. The causal relationship is negative, which formally excludes the possibility of a necessary condition relationship between events investigated. However, the same data simultaneously provide evidence supporting the presence of a necessary condition ($\tilde{\chi}^2 < 3.8$), which is contradictory. Due to this inconsistency, the data were excluded from further analysis. At this point, it is unclear whether these contradictions are attributable to the sensitivity of the laboratory kit used, uncertainties in establishing the correct diagnosis, or whether other factors may have played a role. This issue should be addressed elsewhere.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

⁷Marchini B, Dolcher MP, Sabbatini A, Klein G, Migliorini P. Immune response to different sequences of the EBNA I molecule in Epstein-Barr virus-related disorders and in autoimmune diseases. *J Autoimmun.* 1994 Apr;7(2):179-91. doi: 10.1006/jaut.1994.1014. PMID: 7518683.

Study by Toda et al., 1994 (Japan)

Toda⁸ et al. (see [Toda et al., 1994](#)) conducted a study in Japan involving 62 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 47 healthy controls. They used an indirect immunofluorescence (IF) assay to evaluate the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), specifically measuring IgG antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA), the early antigen (EA), and EBV nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 7. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 7. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 15. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Toda et al. , 1994).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	61	40	101
	NO	0	6	6
		61	46	107

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = 0,28067320$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00518293
 $p(SINE) = 1,00000000$

P VALUES.
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(SINE - Not A_t) = 0,00$
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(SINE - B_t) = 0,00$
 P Value (SINE) = 0,00000000

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(IOU) = 0,51401869$
 $p(IOI) = 0,37383178$

The data published by Toda et al. impress with a $p(IOU) = 0,514018692$ ([Barukčić, 2019a](#)) in the negative. The design of this study can be regarded as highly unfair. With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Toda et al. are potentially biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Toda et al. were able to provide very strong evidence, that EBV VCA IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjögren's syndrome (causal relationship > 0 ; necessary condition = 1 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2(SINE - Not A_t) = 0$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(SINE - B_t) = 0$; P-Value = 0). We reject the alternative hypothesis and retain the null hypothesis. For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV VCA IgG Pos. , no Sjögren's syndrome .**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

⁸Toda I, Ono M, Fujishima H, Tsubota K. Sjögren's syndrome (SS) and Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) reactivation. *Ocul Immunol Inflamm.* 1994;2(2):101-9. doi: 10.3109/09273949409057066. PMID: 22823080.

Study by Gao et al., 2010 (China)

Gao⁹ et al. (see Gao et al., 2010) conducted a study involving 29 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 44 healthy controls. They employed an ELISA assay to assess the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), specifically measuring IgM antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA) and IgG antibodies to both VCA and the early antigen (EA).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 8. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 8. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 16. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjören's syndrome (Study of Gao et al. , 2010).

		Sjören's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	29	43	72
	NO	0	1	1
		29	44	73

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k = 0,09567675

p (SINE) = 1,00000000

P VALUES.

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,00

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,00

P Value (SINE) = 0,00000000

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,38356164

p(IOI)= 0,58904110

The data published by Gao et al. impress with a p(IOU) = 0,383561644 (Barukčić, 2019a) in the negative. The design of this study can be regarded as very unfair . With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of are potentially biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Gao et al. were able to provide very strong evidence, that EBV VCA IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjören's syndrome (causal relationship > 0; necessary condition = 1 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0 ; P-Value = 0). We reject the alternative hypothesis and retain the null hypothesis. For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV VCA IgG Pos. , no Sjören's syndrome .**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

⁹Gao C, Xin M, Liu X, Chao Y, Luo B. Detection and Significance of Epstein Barr Virus Markers in Peripheral Blood of Patients with Primary Sjogren's Syndrome. Prog Modern Biomed (2010) 10(20):3900–2.

Study by Pasoto et al., 2013 (Brazil)

Pasoto¹⁰ et al. (see Pasoto et al., 2013) conducted a study involving 100 patients with Sjögren's syndrome (SjS) and 89 healthy controls. They employed an ELISA assay to evaluate the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), specifically measuring IgM antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA), and IgG antibodies to VCA, the early antigen (EA), and EBV nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 9. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 9. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 17. Relationship: EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Pasoto et al. , 2013).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos.	YES	92	84	176
	NO	8	5	13
		100	89	189

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,04697998$
 p (SINE) = 0,95767196
P VALUES.
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_i) = 0,64
 P Value (SINE) = 0,04144472
STUDY DESIGN.
 p (IOU)= 0,46031746
 p (IOI)= 0,40211640

The data from the study by Pasoto et al., 2013 (Brazil) are inconsistent and, therefore, could not be included in this analysis. The causal relationship is negative, which formally excludes the possibility of a necessary condition relationship between events investigated. However, the same data simultaneously provide evidence supporting the presence of a necessary condition ($\tilde{\chi}^2 < 3.8$; P-Value < 0.05), which is contradictory. Due to this inconsistency, the data were excluded from further analysis. At this point, it is unclear whether these contradictions are attributable to the sensitivity of the laboratory kit used, uncertainties in establishing the correct diagnosis, or whether other factors may have played a role. This issue should be addressed elsewhere.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

¹⁰Pasoto SG, Natalino RR, Chakkour HP, Viana Vdos S, Bueno C, Leon EP, Vendramini MB, Neto ML, Bonfa E. EBV reactivation serological profile in primary Sjögren's syndrome: an underlying trigger of active articular involvement? *Rheumatol Int.* 2013 May;33(5):1149-57. doi: 10.1007/s00296-012-2504-3. Epub 2012 Sep 6. PMID: 22955798.

Study by Kivity et al., 2014 (Israel)

Kivity¹¹ et al. (see Kivity et al., 2014) conducted a study involving 82 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 139 healthy controls. They utilized a multiplex assay to evaluate the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), specifically including IgM antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA), IgG antibodies to VCA, IgG antibodies to the early antigen (EA), and IgG antibodies to EBV nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 10. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 10. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 18. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Kivity et al. , 2014).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	70	129	199
	NO	12	10	22
		82	139	221

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,12004488$
 p (SINE) = 0,94570136
P VALUES.
 χ^2 (SINE— B_t) = 1,76
STUDY DESIGN.
 p (IOU)= 0,27149321
 p (IOD)= 0,52941176

The data from the study by Kivity et al., 2014 (Israel) are inconsistent and, therefore, could not be included in this analysis. The causal relationship is negative, which formally excludes the possibility of a necessary condition relationship between events investigated. However, the same data simultaneously provide evidence supporting the presence of a necessary condition ($\tilde{\chi}^2 < 3.8$), which is contradictory. Due to this inconsistency, the data were excluded from further analysis. At this point, it is unclear whether these contradictions are attributable to the sensitivity of the laboratory kit used, uncertainties in establishing the correct diagnosis, or whether other factors may have played a role. This issue should be addressed elsewhere. This issue should be addressed elsewhere.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

¹¹Kivity S, Arango MT, Ehrenfeld M, Tehori O, Shoenfeld Y, Anaya JM, Agmon-Levin N. Infection and autoimmunity in Sjogren's syndrome: a clinical study and comprehensive review. *J Autoimmun.* 2014 Jun;51:17-22. doi: 10.1016/j.jaut.2014.02.008. Epub 2014 Mar 15. PMID: 24637076.

Study by Li et al., 2014 (China)

Li¹² et al. (see Li et al., 2014) conducted a study involving 75 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 74 healthy controls. They used an ELISA assay to evaluate the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), specifically measuring IgM antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA), and IgG antibodies to VCA and the early antigen (EA).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 11. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 11. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 19. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Li et al. , 2014).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	75	71	146
	NO	0	3	3
		75	74	149

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,14431085$

p (SINE) = 1,00000000

P VALUES.

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,00

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,00

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,48322148

p(IOI)= 0,47651007

The data published by Li et al. impress with a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,483221477$ (Barukčić, 2019a) in the negative. The design of this study can be regarded as very unfair. With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Li et al. are potentially biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Li et al. were able to provide very slight evidence, that EBV VCA IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjögren's syndrome (causal relationship > 0 ; necessary condition = 1 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0 ; P-Value = 0). We reject the alternative hypothesis and retain the null hypothesis. For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV VCA IgG Pos. , no Sjögren's syndrome .**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

¹²Li H, Wang J, Wang L. Analysis of the situation of EB virus infection in patients with Sjögren's syndrome. Chin J Nosocomiol (2014) 24(24):6154–5.

Study by Yang et al., 2015 (China)

Yang¹³ et al. (see [Yang and Fu, 2015](#)) investigated 39 Sjögren's syndrome patients and 22 healthy controls in China using ELISA to detect IgG-anti-EBNA1 antibodies.

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 12. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 12. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 20. Relationship: EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Yang et al., 2015).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos.	YES	35	22	57
	NO	4	0	4
		39	22	61

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,19896267$
 $p(SINE) = 0,93442623$

P VALUES.
 $\chi^2(SINE - B_t) = 0,41$

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(IOUS) = 0,57377049$
 $p(IOD) = 0,29508197$

The data from the study by Zhang et al., 2019 (China) are inconsistent and, therefore, could not be included in this analysis. The causal relationship is negative, which formally excludes the possibility of a necessary condition relationship between events investigated. However, the same data simultaneously provide evidence supporting the presence of a necessary condition ($\tilde{\chi}^2 < 3.8$), which is contradictory. Due to this inconsistency, the data were excluded from further analysis. At this point, it is unclear whether these contradictions are attributable to the sensitivity of the laboratory kit used, uncertainties in establishing the correct diagnosis, or whether other factors may have played a role. This issue should be addressed elsewhere.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

¹³Yang L, Fu P. Expression of EBNA1 and EBNA2 in the labial salivary gland of patients with sicca syndrome. *J Clin Dermatol* (2015) 44(2):73–7.

Study by Zhang et al., 2019 (China)

Zhang¹⁴ et al.(see Zhang et al., 2019) conducted a study involving 72 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 60 healthy controls. They utilized an ELISA assay to assess the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), specifically measuring IgM antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA), and IgG antibodies to VCA, the early antigen (EA), and EBV nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 13. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 13. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 21. Relationship: EBV VCA IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Zhang et al. , 2019).

		Sjören's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV VCA IgG Pos.	YES	70	59	129
	NO	2	1	3
		72	60	132

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship k = -0,03712307
p (SINE) = 0,98484848
P VALUES.
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_i) = 1,33
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_i) = 0,06
STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,52272727
p(IOD)= 0,43181818

The data from the study by Zhang et al., 2019 (China) are inconsistent and, therefore, could not be included in this analysis. The causal relationship is negative, which formally excludes the possibility of a necessary condition relationship between events investigated. However, the same data simultaneously provide evidence supporting the presence of a necessary condition ($\tilde{\chi}^2 < 3.8$; P-Value < 0.05), which is contradictory. Due to this inconsistency, the data were excluded from further analysis. At this point, it is unclear whether these contradictions are attributable to the sensitivity of the laboratory kit used, uncertainties in establishing the correct diagnosis, or whether other factors may have played a role. This issue should be addressed elsewhere.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

¹⁴Zhang L, Wang R, Zhou Y, Zhang G. Correlation between Epstein-Barr virus and Sjögren's syndrome. Chin Remedies Clinics (2019) 19(4):556–9.

Study by Xuan et al., 2020 (China)

Xuan¹⁵ et al. (see Xuan et al., 2020) conducted an investigation involving 119 patients with Sjögren's syndrome and 65 healthy controls. The study assessed the presence of antibodies against Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), including IgM antibodies to the viral capsid antigen (VCA), IgG antibodies to VCA, IgG antibodies to the early antigen (EA), and IgG antibodies to EBV nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA1).

H0: NULL HYPOTHESIS 14. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS TRUE.

HA: ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS 14. WITHOUT EBV INFECTION, NO SJÖGREN'S SYNDROME IS FALSE.

Proof by a single study. The statistical analysis of the available data is as follows.

Table 22. Relationship: EBV IgG Pos. and Sjögren's syndrome (Study of Xuan et al. , 2020).

		Sjögren's syndrome		
		YES	NO	
EBV IgG Pos.	YES	117	62	179
	NO	2	3	5
		119	65	184

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,08627484$
 $p(SINE) = 0,98913043$
 $p(SINE) \text{ approx.} = 1 - (c/B) > 0,98319328$
 $p(SINE) \text{ approx.} = 1 - (c/(Not A)) > 0,60000000$

P VALUES.

$\chi^2(SINE - Not A_c) = 0,80$
 $\chi^2(SINE - B_c) = 0,03$
P Value (SINE) = **0,01081070**

STUDY DESIGN.

$p(IOUS) = 0,61956522$
 $p(IOI) = 0,32608696$

The data published by Xuan et al. impress with a $p(IOUS) = 0,619565217$ (Barukčić, 2019a) in the negative. The design of this study can be regarded as highly unfair. With some restrictions, we are authorized to assume that the data from the study of Xuan et al. are biased. In other words, the data are of restricted use for our purposes. Despite all adversities, including an unsuitable study design and unknown sensitivity of the methods used, Xuan et al. were able to demonstrate that EBV IgG Pos. is a necessary condition for Sjögren's syndrome (causal relationship > 0 ; necessary condition = $0,989130435$; P-Value = $0,010869565$). We must reject the alternative hypothesis and retain the null hypothesis. For now, and until further evidence suggests otherwise, we may conclude: **Without EBV IgG Pos. , no Sjögren's syndrome .**

Quod erat demonstrandum.

¹⁵Xuan J, Ji Z, Wang B, Zeng X, Chen R, He Y, Rao P, Wu P, Shi G. Serological Evidence for the Association Between Epstein-Barr Virus Infection and Sjögren's Syndrome. *Front Immunol.* 2020 Oct 30;11:590444. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2020.590444. PMID: 33193425; PMCID: PMC7662096.

4. Discussion

The analysis of a necessary condition relationship between an Epstein-Barr virus infection and a particular disease is inherently complex. Within the framework of a case-control study, one would expect that 100% of the affected individuals would also be EBV positive. This group is then compared to a control group of healthy individuals, i.e., those without the disease in question. However, the prevalence of EBV infection is increasing with age (see Cui et al., 2018). Therefore, depending on age, the prevalence of EBV infection in such a control group could likewise approach 100%. In light of these circumstances, the challenge arises of reliably identifying a necessary condition for the disease. To address such and other theoretically conceivable difficulties, appropriate countermeasures are necessary. When addressing the challenge of identifying a necessary condition for a disease like Sjögren's syndrome in the context of high EBV prevalence among control groups, one possible strategy is to select a control group in which the prevalence of EBV infection is deliberately lower than in the age-matched cohort of the affected population. Specifically, the prevalence of EBV infection in this control group could be targeted to be approximately 10% below the prevalence observed in the cohort with the disease. This approach is intended to create a clearer distinction between the two groups, thereby enhancing the ability to detect a relationship between EBV infection and the disease in question. However, this strategy is not without potential drawbacks. Most importantly, depending on the statistical methods used, such a strategy can introduce bias into the study, particularly if the control group differs significantly from the disease group in other ways beyond EBV prevalence. For example, if age itself were a necessary condition for the disease (i.e., if older age is strongly associated with both EBV infection and the disease), then selecting a younger control group with lower EBV prevalence could obscure the true relationship between EBV and the disease. Usually, the control group is representative of the general population without the disease, differing from the case group primarily by the presence of the disease or outcome in question. Such a strategy could undermine the validity of the study's conclusions, as the groups would differ on a key variable other than the one under investigation. Moreover, many statistical methods rely on the assumption that control and disease groups are comparable and may not tolerate such an approach. Introducing a control group with systematically different characteristics may violate this assumption, potentially undermining the validity of the analysis and leading to incorrect inferences and inaccurate results. Given some of the potential issues discussed, theoretically it is possible to consider alternative strategies that could help address the problem of high EBV prevalence in control groups:

1. **Stratified Analysis:** One approach could be to perform a stratified analysis, where the study population is divided into subgroups based on age or other relevant variables. By comparing cases and controls within the same strata, the influence of confounding factors like age can be tried to be minimized. This approach could lead to a more accurate assessment of the relationship between EBV infection and the disease within each subgroup.
2. **Matching:** Another strategy could be to match cases and controls on key variables such as age, sex, or other demographic factors. By ensuring that cases and controls are similar with respect to these variables, a study can try to more effectively isolate the impact of EBV infection on

the disease outcome. This matching process could help to reduce the risk of confounding and increases the comparability of the groups.

3. **Use of Multiple Control Groups:** Employing multiple control groups with varying EBV prevalences is another possible solution. For instance, one control group could be selected to match the age distribution of the disease group, while another could be chosen to have a lower EBV prevalence. This would allow the researchers to compare results across different control groups and assess the robustness of the findings.
4. **Longitudinal Studies:** Finally, a longitudinal study design could be used, where individuals are followed over time to observe the development of the disease in relation to their EBV status.

However, advanced statistical methods, such as necessary condition relationship, can be employed to adjust for differences between groups. These techniques are robust to group differences and do not require additional methods to control for confounding factors, thereby providing a more accurate estimate of the relationship between EBV infection and the disease. As an example, consider the relationship between gaseous oxygen and a burning candle. It does not matter whether the candle is new or old, large or small, red or yellow. All these differences between groups have no impact on the fundamental fact that without gaseous oxygen, no burning candle. This illustrates how certain relationships, such as the one between oxygen and combustion, are independent of other variables, underscoring the importance of necessary conditions in understanding causal relationships. The strategy to select a control group with a lower EBV prevalence may be a useful measure in certain contexts. However, it is important to carefully consider the statistical methods used and the potential biases and challenges this approach may introduce. Depending on the specific research question and study design, alternative methods such necessary condition relationship may offer more robust solutions to the problem of high EBV prevalence in control groups. Such an approach would only introduce bias if age itself were a necessary condition for the disease in question, a hypothesis that can typically be quickly ruled out.

Another challenge is the issue of sensitivity of diagnostic methods used. Sensitivity (see [Yerushalmy, 1947b](#)) directly impacts the accuracy and quality of the collected data. It measures the ability of a diagnostic method to correctly identify individuals who truly have a certain condition. To access and accurately interpret scientific study data, it is crucial to understand the sensitivity of a diagnostic method used. A method with low sensitivity, for example, may fail to detect a significant proportion of individuals who are actually infected or ill. This can significantly affect the validity of the study results. Therefore, specifying the sensitivity of the diagnostic methods used is essential to ensure reliable and reproducible results in research. To illustrate, consider sensitivity in relation to detecting Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) in individuals known to be EBV-positive. Suppose 100 individuals who are confirmed to be EBV-positive are tested using a diagnostic method. If the method correctly identifies 95 of these 100 infected individuals as EBV-positive, it means the method cannot detect all cases. Consequently, the method fails to identify five EBV-positive individuals, resulting in five false-negative results. The sensitivity of this method can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{\text{Number of Positives Detected by the Method}}{\text{Total Number of Actual Positives}} = \frac{95}{100} = 0,95 = 95\%$$

A sensitivity of 95% means that the method correctly diagnoses EBV in 95% of cases where the individual is truly EBV-positive. The remaining 5% represent cases where the method fails to detect an EBV infection despite its presence. Such false-negative results can be problematic in clinical or epidemiological studies, as they may lead to an underestimation of the prevalence of EBV infections and result in incorrect conclusions. Sensitivity of a method has a direct impact on assessing necessary conditions. Let us assume that a necessary condition is theoretically present in 100% of both cases and controls. Given a sensitivity of 95%, this necessary condition should be detected in at least 95% of the cases and controls. Thus, the sensitivity of the method influences the choice of the minimum significance level, α . For certain analyses, it may be advisable to set the significance level α to a value greater than or equal to the sensitivity level of the diagnostic method used.

The analyzed studies were ultimately very contradictory. As a result, several studies had to be excluded (see [Marchini et al., 1994](#); [Pasoto et al., 2013](#); [Kivity et al., 2014](#); [Yang and Fu, 2015](#); [Zhang et al., 2019](#)) due to inconsistencies. In the end, only a few studies could undergo a thorough analysis (see [Venables et al., 1985](#); [Yamaoka et al., 1988](#); [Venables et al., 1989](#); [Inoue et al., 1991](#); [Yang, 1991](#); [Toda et al., 1994](#); [Gao et al., 2010](#); [Li et al., 2014](#); [Xuan et al., 2020](#)). All of the included studies support the null hypothesis: **without** EBV infection, **no** Sjögren's syndrome. Further investigations in this area would certainly be useful and beneficial. However, it seems essential to us that standardized diagnostic criteria, the specification of the sensitivity of the methods used, and a sound study design should be implemented in this context.

5. Conclusion

The analyses presented in this publication lead to the following unequivocal conclusion:

‘Without EBV infection, no Sjögren’s syndrome.’

It is highly likely that within EBV the cause of Sjögren's syndrome will be identified.

Acknowledgments

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some typographical errors appeared in the previous publications, particularly in the definitions section. Efforts have been made and will be made to correct these errors as soon as possible to the extent necessary.

Private note

Empty.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are frequently used:

CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBV	Epstein-Bar virus
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
ISH	In situ hybridization
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
BMI	body mass index
ESRD	end-stage renal disease
HD	hemodialysis
CABG	coronary artery bypass graft
CCI	Charlson comorbidity index
AMI	acute myocardial infarction
MACE	major adverse cardiovascular events
LDL-C	low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
STEMI	ST elevation myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	non-ST elevation myocardial infarction
MI	myocardial infarction
ARB	angiotensin receptor blocker
ACEI	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors
CCBs	calcium channel blockers
IOR	index of relationship
p(IOU)	index of unfairness
p(IOI)	index of independence
k	Causal relationship
SINE	Necessary condition relationship
IMP	Sufficient condition relationship
EXCL	exclusion relationship
RR	Relative risk
RR (nc)	relative risk (necessary condition)
RR (sc)	relative risk (sufficient condition)
OR	Odds ratio
P Value	Probability of significance

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Associated Data

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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